

LEGAL BASIS OF ENSURING PUBLIC ORDER AND SAFETY OF CITIZENS BY INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES.

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Abstract: The article analyzes the specific features of the concepts of public order and security, as well as the theoretical and legal basis of the reforms implemented today.

Key words: Public, order, maintenance, security, provision, public order, public security, threat, strategy, tactics, activity, government agency, legislation.

Today, the changes taking place in the political and social life of our state, especially the tasks related to the security and stability of our country, require an extremely serious approach. Within the framework of ongoing reforms, special attention is being paid to strengthening law and order and legality in our country, preserving and reinforcing our peaceful and tranquil life, and ensuring the guaranteed security of our people.

This is being achieved through the introduction of modern working methods in forming a comprehensive system for ensuring legitimacy and public order and security, preventing offenses, and combating crime.

As President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev emphasized, "it would not be an exaggeration to say that there is not a single state or society that is not concerned about the alarming situation and the political and economic crises currently prevailing on a global scale."

In particular, international terrorism, extremism, drug trafficking, religious confrontation, illegal migration, human trafficking, environmental problems, and the increasing economic hardship, unemployment, and poverty in some regions are causing serious concern to all of humanity.

The more society develops, the more crucial it becomes for all citizens to observe the requirements of public order and safety, and to be intolerant of any antisocial phenomena. The necessity of ensuring public order and security, as well as strict adherence to the norms regulating social relations in this area, is linked to the interests of the people, the state, and society.

Laws and legislative acts of state bodies aimed at ensuring public order and security play a special role in regulating relations in the field of public order and security, while constitutional norms occupy a central place in the regulation of social norms.

For example, according to Article 71 of our main constitution, "The establishment and activities of political parties and public associations that aim to forcibly change the constitutional order, oppose the sovereignty, integrity and security of the republic, the constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens, promote war, social, national, racial and religious enmity, encroach upon the health and morality of the people, as well as militarized associations, political parties and public associations of a national and religious nature are prohibited. The formation of secret societies and associations is prohibited." [2]

Norms defining relations in the field of public order and safety are also contained in criminal laws and other legislative acts. Such norms are reflected in the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees of the President of the country, resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers, as well as in other documents of the representative and executive authorities of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional administrations and the city of Tashkent, and normative legal acts of local authorities.

A number of laws aimed at ensuring public order and safety in our country have been adopted and are being implemented, including the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Sanitary Supervision" (1992), "On Nature Protection" (1992), "On Protection of Atmospheric Air" (1996), "On Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances" (1999), "On Protection of Population and Territories from Natural and Man-made Emergency Situations" (1999), "On Civil Protection" (2000), "On Radiation Safety" (2000), "On Combating Terrorism" (2000), "On Transit of Special Cargo and Military Formations" (2001), "On Automobile Roads" (2007), "On Fire Safety" (2009), "On Road Traffic Safety" (2013), "On Prevention of Offenses" (2014), "On Sanitary and Epidemiological Welfare of the Population" (2015), "On Labor Protection" (1993, 2016), "On Protection and Use of Flora" (1997, 2016), "On Protection and Use of Fauna" (1997, 2016), "On Combating Corruption" (2017), "On Combating Extremism" (2018), and "On Protection of Population and Territories from Natural and Man-made Emergency Situations" (2022).

At the same time, extensive work is being carried out to ensure that the actions of internal affairs bodies are systematic, precise, and lawful, based on rules and conclusions derived from comprehensive critical analysis, in accordance with the tasks outlined in the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan"[3], No. UP-60 of January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026"[4], and No. UP-158 of September 11, 2023 "On the Strategy 'Uzbekistan - 2030'"[5], and these are being continuously improved.

Significant work is being carried out to develop and strengthen the lower levels of internal affairs bodies organized to maintain public order, ensure citizen safety, prevent offenses, and combat crime in mahallas.

Specifically, the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5005 of April 10, 2017 [6] and No. UP-6196 of March 26, 2021 [7] defined the most important directions for reforming the system of internal affairs bodies.

These directions fully encompass the system of ensuring public order and security by internal affairs bodies. Resolution No. PP-2940 of May 1, 2017 "On measures to fundamentally improve the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of maintaining public order and ensuring security," Resolution No. PP-3528 of February 14, 2018 "On introducing a qualitatively new system of maintaining public order, preventing offenses and combating crime in Tashkent city," Resolution No. PP-3786 of June 19, 2018 "On additional measures to improve the effectiveness of maintaining public order, prevention of offenses and combating crime in Tashkent city,"

Resolution No. PP-4075 of December 24, 2018 "On additional measures to improve the effectiveness of ensuring public safety," and Resolution No. PP-5050 of April 2, 2021 "On additional organizational measures to further improve the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of ensuring public safety and combating crime," as well as the comprehensive

measures adopted and gradually implemented within their framework, provide for the formation of a new system of ensuring public order and safety in the country and in each of its administrative-territorial units.

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These areas also fully cover the system of ensuring public order and security of internal affairs bodies. 2017

This dissertation research, to a certain extent, serves to fulfill the tasks outlined in the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-2940 of May 1 "On measures to fundamentally improve the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of maintaining public order and ensuring security," No. PP-3528 of February 14, 2018 "On the introduction of a qualitatively new system for maintaining public order, preventing offenses and combating crime in the city of Tashkent," No. PP-3786 of June 19, 2018 "On additional measures to ensure public

Resolution No. PP-4075 of December 24, 2018, "On Additional Measures to Enhance the Effectiveness of Public Security," and Resolution No. PP-5050 of April 2, 2021, "On Additional Organizational Measures to Further Improve the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies in the Field of Ensuring Public Security and Combating Crime," as well as the comprehensive measures adopted and implemented in practice as part of their implementation, provide for the formation of a new system for ensuring public order and security in the country, in each of its administrative and territorial units

Effective management of the newly formed system of internal affairs bodies to ensure public order and security in the country and all its territorial units requires a high level of professional competence and dedication from each leader.

In this regard, a special place is occupied by Presidential Decree No. 27, signed on November 29, 2021, on the introduction of a new system for ensuring public safety in Uzbekistan [8]. Over the past period, for the first time in our country, the main directions of state policy in the field of ensuring public safety, mechanisms for its implementation, and specific tasks of 10 ministries and agencies ensuring public safety have been identified. These include the Cabinet of Ministers, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the State Security Service, the Ministry of Emergency Situations, the Prosecutor General's Office, the Ministry of Mahalla and Family Support, the Ministry for the Development of Information Technologies and Communications, the Ministry of Health, and local khokimiyats. This has been crucial in organizing the implementation of the decree and establishing effective cooperation between the entities.

Based on this decree, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-155 dated April 11, 2024, was adopted [9].

According to it, the appointment of the Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan as the head of the republican special commission for oversight of the organization of public safety at cultural, trade, and service facilities is of great importance.

These regulatory documents adopted by the head of our state include a number of tasks, such as improving the activities of internal affairs bodies, regulating them, preventing offenses, ensuring public order and security, and combating crime.

Within the framework of the large-scale reforms being implemented, special attention is paid to ensuring a peaceful and orderly life of the population and forming a culture of

lawfulness and public safety in our society. Completely new mechanisms and procedures for organizing work to ensure public safety based on the principle of "serving the interests of the people" have been introduced, and targeted cooperation between state bodies and public structures has been established.

This, in turn, involves identifying and suppressing terrorist and extremist activities of any kind; combating corruption, crimes, and offenses related to narcotic and psychotropic substances, weapons, ammunition, explosives, illegal migration, and human trafficking; as well as protecting human rights and freedoms. It also includes ensuring the continuous and safe operation of tourist facilities, improving vehicle safety standards and traffic rules to prevent injuries and deaths caused by road accidents, and preventing repeated offenses by citizens. Additionally, it involves protecting the population and territories from natural and man-made emergencies, enhancing civil defense, developing and continuously improving the population's skills in fire safety, and implementing a qualitatively new system for ensuring public safety, peace, and tranquility of the population. These measures aim to introduce reliable and effective mechanisms for ensuring the security of individuals, society, and the state, and successfully fulfilling the tasks of maintaining public order and safety and combating crime.

In conclusion, it can be said that maintaining public order and ensuring the safety of citizens is one of the important issues in all countries, and the management of structural units involved in this task is carried out through various ways, methods, and approaches. It also depends on each country's unique experience in this area and the extent to which it can implement it..

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